

Combining Sentinel-1 with PALSAR-2 for land surface deformation monitoring across Arctic lowland permafrost areas

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Abstract

Synthetic aperture radar (SAR)-derived land surface deformation from SAR interferometry can serve as indication for potential permafrost degradation. Long-term (multi-annual) as well as seasonal (unfrozen period) deformation are of interest in this context. However, SAR mission acquisition strategies, atmospheric and ionospheric effects and frequency limit its applicability. Therefore, a dual-mission strategy has been adopted in our study. Sentinel-1 (C-band) has been primarily investigated but in combination with PALSAR-2 (L-band) observations to compile a dataset representing different permafrost landscape patterns and to derive both seasonal and long-term deformation. Seasonal patterns were found to differ significantly from long-term patterns. Spatial filtering, applied to correct for atmospheric and ionospheric disturbances, leads to centering of the density distribution around zero. The resulting positive deformation patterns largely coincide with dry and barren tundra types, which are likely stable areas. This needs to be accounted for when interpreting the results. A Random Forest regressor analysis was used to identify driving features for both seasonal and long-term deformation. Considered parameters included land cover, soil properties, permafrost active layer thickness & mean annual ground temperature, and disturbances. Both long-term and seasonal deformation reflected land cover (vegetation patterns) in addition to disturbances (fires) in Arctic lowland permafrost regions. Results indicate the potential utility of land cover and vegetation information for the prediction of deformation patterns, but model fitting scores were only

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weak to moderate. The predictive potential is higher for seasonal than for long-term rates, particularly when considering multiple parameters.

Keywords: InSAR, Arctic, permafrost

1. Introduction

C-band synthetic aperture radar (SAR) observations from space have been shown of high value for Arctic permafrost monitoring (Bartsch et al., 2023a). Permafrost is an Essential Climate Variable (ECV; Global Climate Observing System GCOS (2022)) but its monitoring is very challenging as it is a subsurface phenomenon. Satellite observations nevertheless provide valuable proxies, including related land surface properties and indicators of permafrost degradation. Already ERS (European Remote Sensing satellite, 1991-2011) and ENVISAT ASAR (Environmental Satellite Advanced SAR, 2002-2012) C-band observations were used to describe permafrost environments through for example surface state (Wismann, 2000; Park et al., 2011), surface roughness as proxy for wetlands and soil properties (Reschke et al., 2012; Bartsch et al., 2016), and ground fast lake ice (Duguay et al., 2002; Surdu et al., 2014; Bartsch et al., 2017). The availability of Sentinel-1 from 2014 onward sparked new developments such as tundra vegetation height retrieval (Bartsch et al., 2020b) and an extensive investigation of permafrost landscape subsidence patterns through SAR Interferometry (InSAR) (Zwieback et al., 2024b). Already the ERS InSAR derived seasonal variations in ground deformation were proposed to reflect thaw depth (incl. permafrost active layer thickness, Liu et al. (2010, 2012)).

Permafrost soils contain ice in various forms. The ground subsides when this ice melts due to seasonal (unfrozen period) thaw or long-term (multi-annual) changes. Observed deformations are comparably small. They are usually in the order of a few centimeters within a certain season (Streletskiy et al., 2025). In situ measurements are still rare. Remote sensing has proven as an alternative since SAR Interferometry (InSAR) can detect such subtle changes (e.g., Short et al. (2011); Liu et al. (2012); Rouyet et al. (2019); Strozzi et al. (2018)). Zwieback et al. (2024b) summarized applications of InSAR in permafrost areas to date. This included seasonal phenomena, thermokarst with a separate discussion on fires and soil creep on hill slopes, spanning not only Arctic lowlands but also the Qinghai-Tibet

33 Plateau. Recently, also airborne campaigns provided insight into specifically
34 seasonal patterns (Wig et al., 2025).

35
36 A range of studies were initiated across the Arctic with the launch of
37 the Sentinel-1 mission in 2014. Its capabilities for long-term deformation
38 across several Arctic and Antarctic lowland sites with continuous permafrost
39 were demonstrated by Strozzi et al. (2018) (2015-2018). The added value
40 of Sentinel-1 is, however, the potential to analyze seasonal patterns. Chen
41 et al. (2018) focused on a site with Yedoma soils in the Lena Delta and the
42 years 2016 and 2017. A Yedoma elevation dependence for seasonal defor-
43 mation was found. Subsidence was more pronounced in Yedoma uplands.
44 Issues at the beginning of thaw were identified, specifically heave before ac-
45 tual subsidence was observed. The seasonal thaw progression was further
46 studied in detail on the Yamal peninsula (Bartsch et al., 2019). Differences
47 between soil types were found in general and in unusually warm summers,
48 specifically during the late summer season. Results were cross-compared
49 to in situ data as well as X-Band observations (COSMO Skymed). Good
50 agreement was found with the shorter X-band suggesting limited influence
51 of dynamic phenomena which potentially impact signal penetration depth at
52 C-band, specifically related to soil moisture variations. Further on, Bartsch
53 et al. (2019) suggested seasonal time series analyses considering the cumu-
54 lative positive degree days of thaw (DDT), instead of the use of day of year
55 to facilitate comparison across different years. An X-band comparison to
56 Sentinel-1 derived seasonal deformation was also made for Adventdalen on
57 Svalbard by Rouyet et al. (2019) with a focus on geomorphological features
58 as the study site comprised a river floodplain and hill slopes. This study
59 was extended to two more sites and a comparison to a permafrost related
60 deformation model was made (Rouyet et al., 2021). A Sentinel-1 study on
61 fire scars was published by Yanagiya and Furuya (2020) focusing on a site in
62 Siberia. Results were compared to L-band. The added value of Sentinel-1 was
63 the denser time series which also allowed to describe heave during freeze-up.
64 This study was later extended in years and additional fire scars in the same
65 region (Yanagiya et al., 2023). Discontinuous permafrost was studied with
66 Sentinel-1 in the Canadian Arctic (Northern Quebec)(Wang et al., 2020),
67 demonstrating the limitation for C-band application in shrub and forest en-
68 vironment. The late summer season including warmer summers were also
69 studied by Zwieback and Meyer (2021) for the Alaskan North Slope. Ground
70 ice records could be obtained to explain the found deformation patterns. In

71 the following, specifically excess ground ice has been investigated (Zwieback
72 et al., 2024a). Sentinel-1 seasonal deformation patterns were also interpreted
73 from a geomorphological perspective for the Indigirka lowlands in Northern
74 Siberia (van Huissteden et al., 2021). Yedoma soils showed heave in wet years
75 indicating ground ice aggradation. Years with unusual flooding led to more
76 subsidence in the floodplains. Teshebaeva et al. (2021) used Sentinel-1 for
77 documenting pronounced subsidence with the persistent scatterer technique
78 in the proximity to a settlement on central Yamal. Hot spots of subsidence
79 were identified in the proximity of a gas field as well as in some tundra ar-
80 eas. Guan et al. (2024) documented Sentinel-1 InSAR results (2018-2021)
81 in three regions across Northern America, describing the various phenomena
82 such as fires and pronounced seasonal subsidence in wetter areas. In addi-
83 tion to Sentinel-1, also Radarsat has been used to demonstrate the C-band
84 capabilities across permafrost regions (e.g. Short et al. (2011), Samsonov
85 et al. (2016) documenting pingo growth, Rudy et al. (2018)). A multitude of
86 permafrost related studies based on C-band missions has been also carried
87 out across the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau (Zwieback et al., 2024b).

88
89 In situ observations considered in InSAR Arctic lowland permafrost stud-
90 ies typically include active layer measurements. In some cases also linkage
91 to ground ice (Zwieback et al., 2024a; Scheer et al., 2023) and soil moisture
92 (Widhalm et al., 2025) conditions was investigated. Comparison of Sentinel-1
93 subsidence to actual in situ subsidence measurements was so far only shown
94 for central Yamal (Russia) and in the Inuvik region (Canada) (Bartsch et al.,
95 2019; Widhalm et al., 2025). This reflects the limited availability of such mea-
96 surements. Streletskiy et al. (2025) provided an overview of subsidence in
97 situ measurement. The availability is limited for Siberia. But measurements
98 have been published for Alaska North Slope and NW territories, Canada (e.g.
99 O'Neill et al. (2023)).

100
101 Bartsch et al. (2019) exemplified that there can be distinct seasonal defor-
102 mation patterns (based on Sentinel-1) depending on land cover type (central
103 Yamal). Wig et al. (2025) identified similarities between NDVI (Normalized
104 Difference Vegetation Index) trends (in case of greening) and L- and P-band
105 seasonal deformation from airborne campaign data across Alaska and North-
106 ern Canada (unfrozen season 2017). A relationship with NDVI itself was
107 not found. The majority of available Sentinel-1 based deformation studies,
108 however, focused on the linkage to soil properties, specifically thaw depth.

109 Nevertheless, an analyses of soil parameters is limited due to constraint avail-
110 ability of relevant data. For permafrost landscapes predictor analyses, as for
111 example part of Random forest models, research has so far been limited to
112 land cover and vegetation targeted studies (Olefeldt et al., 2021; Tassone
113 et al., 2024).

114

115 Although the first published study by Strozzi et al. (2018) indicated appli-
116 cability of Sentinel-1 for long-term deformation monitoring, it has not been
117 extensively applied across Arctic lowlands to date. This also applies to com-
118 parisons between seasonal and long-term change across different permafrost
119 landscapes. So far, long-term deformation has predominantly been studied
120 using L-band SAR (see discussion in Bartsch et al. (2023a); Zwieback et al.
121 (2024a)).

122

123 Here, for the first time, we cross-compare long-term and seasonal InSAR-
124 derived deformation across different Arctic permafrost landscapes to advance
125 our understanding of permafrost landscape dynamics and to assess the utility
126 of InSAR analyses primarily based on Sentinel-1 C-band data. L-Band obser-
127 vations from PALSAR-2 (Phased Array L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar)
128 needed to be considered in addition, in order to cover a range of landscapes
129 across the Arctic. Further on, we analyzed the relationship between deforma-
130 tion and environmental parameters (including land cover and soil character-
131 istics) through predictor analyses based on a Random Forest model. As both
132 Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2 observations were used for long-term deformation
133 retrieval, a cross comparison between C- and L-band was conducted.

134

135 **2. Data and study regions**

136 *2.1. Sentinel-1*

137 Sentinel-1 provides observations in C-band (2.6 cm wavelength). The
138 mission encompasses three satellites, A, B and C, launched 2014, 2016 and
139 2024. The analyses period is, however, limited to 2016 to 2021, due to limited
140 observations of Sentinel-1 A for the Arctic in the first years and failure of
141 Sentinel-1 B in the end of 2021. The A/B constellation theoretically enabled
142 a 6-day repeat cycle, but the common interval was nevertheless 12 days for
143 the study regions. Data acquired with the Interferometric Wide (IW) swath
144 mode (2.3 m x 13.9 m) in VV polarization were used. Deformation retrieval

145 was applied to acquisitions within the unfrozen period, what reflects phase
146 change in the active layer. A minimum of six acquisitions were selected per
147 season to ensure robust retrieval of seasonal subsidence (Widhalm et al.,
148 2025). Long-term retrievals were made for 2018 to 2021 (Table 1) and sea-
149 sonal for 2017 - 2023 (Table 2).

150

151 Sentinel-1 data availability, the location of long-term measurement sites
152 and a gradient of permafrost landscapes (ground ice types) determined the
153 choice of the frames. The four regions include distinct settings with ma-
154 rine deposits (Yamal peninsula in Western Siberia), upland tundra (part of
155 Alaska North Slope), peat rich landscapes and floodplains (Widhalm et al.,
156 2025). Tabular ground ice has been documented for Yamal (Leibman et al.,
157 2015). Glacial sediments are dominating the Inuvik region apart from the
158 extensive floodplain of the Mackenzie river and its delta. The Chersky frame
159 includes ice-poor sands (Fyodorov-Davydov et al., 2004), the Kolyma river
160 floodplain and partially organic- and ice-rich Yedoma deposits (Grosse et al.,
161 2013). Thaw lakes are common features in all regions and thus also drained
162 lake basins. The sites represent a bioclimatic gradient and thus different
163 dominating vegetation communities. The Yamal site represents the most
164 northern setting. It is located within the Northern hypo-Arctic tundra (as
165 defined by Walker et al. (2002)). Northern Alaska sites are located within the
166 southern hypo-Arctic tundra and the remaining regions are located within
167 the transition zone to the forest biome. Wildfires are common within the
168 latter zone.

169

170 *2.2. ALOS-2 PALSAR-2*

171 PALSAR-2 aboard JAXA's ALOS-2 satellite provides L-Band SAR data
172 (24 cm wavelength) since 2014. PALSAR-2 data have been used specifically
173 for long-term deformation monitoring. They partially served as substitute
174 for Sentinel-1 where long-term retrieval failed. In addition, data are used for
175 L- to C-band comparisons.

176

177 Acquisitions within the unfrozen season are often limited to one to two
178 scenes across Arctic permafrost regions. This potentially comprises an early
179 thaw season (June to July) and a late thaw season scene. The thaw and
180 freeze-up dates can vary from year to year and between regions. The acqui-
181 sition timings do therefore only partly meet the needs of permafrost defor-

Table 1: Years covered and number of interferograms used for long-term deformation retrieval. P - Palsar-2, S - Sentinel-1. * ascending orbit.

Region	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	#P/S
Inuvik		P	P	P	S*	S*		6/29
Central North Slope		P	P	P/S	P/S	S		10/23
Noatak River Basin			P	P	P/S	S	S	4/38
Yukon-Kuskokwim Delta	P	P	P	P	P			12/0
Chersky				S	S			0/22
Yamal Peninsula			P	P	P			6/0
Sum								38/112

Table 2: Years covered and number of interferograms used for seasonal deformation retrieval based on Sentinel-1.

Region	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Sum
Inuvik			8	10	9	8	8	43
Central North Slope	6		5	8				19
Noatak River Basin	10	9	8	9	8	9		53
Yukon-Kuskokwim Delta	10				10			20
Chersky	6		5	8				19
Yamal Peninsula (9 frames)				25	13			38
Sum	32	9	26	60	40	17	8	192

182 mation monitoring. In general, PALSAR-2 can thus not be used for seasonal
 183 change monitoring. In case of long-term monitoring, the start and end date
 184 should represent a similar seasonal thaw history. Where available, early
 185 season acquisitions have been selected (Table 1). In cases where both was
 186 available (specifically Inuvik), both have been processed in order to inves-
 187 tigate the impact of the selection choice. All used scenes were acquired in
 188 ScanSAR mode, HH polarization, with single look pixel spacing of about 9 m
 189 and 3 m in range and azimuth.

190

191 2.3. Geospatial datasets

192 Burned areas are known to occur in five of the six study regions (Table
 193 3). Different types of datasets have been used to separate them depending
 194 on region. For Alaska, the Alaska Large Fire Database (Kasischke et al.,
 195 2002) starting from 1940 was applied. For Inuvik, the Fire History dataset
 196 from the Government of the Northwest Territories (NWT Centre for Geomat-
 197 ics) starting in 1950 was available. MODIS fire data (ESA CCI Fire 2001-
 198 Lizundia-Loiola et al. (2020)) and Google Earth historical images were used

199 to identify fire events for the Chersky region back to 1993, which were then
 200 digitized using Landsat images (USGS EarthExplorer). A dataset for drained
 201 lake basins derived from Landsat data has been available for the Alaska North
 202 Slope (Bergstedt et al., 2021).

203

Table 3: Study region characteristics. Degree day of thaw (DDT) determined from ERA5, ALT and MAGT from Permafrost_cci (Westermann et al., 2024), slope from Copernicus DEM, infrastructure from Bartsch et al. (2023b), fires from Alaska Fire Database, MWT centre for Geomatics & MODIS/Landsat. Regions: IN - Inuvik, NS - central North Slope, NRB - Noatak River Basin, YKD - Yukon-Kuskokwim Delta, CH - Chersky, YAM - Yamal.

Parameter	IN	NS	NRB	YKD	CH	YAM
Overall size [km ²]	17771	40436	20505	16869	43225	93929
Mean of annual DDT _{max} [°C]	1578	1063	1119	1754	1295	1177
Mean ALT 2019 [m]	0.64	0.61	0.78	0.97	0,42	0,58
Mean MAGT _{2m} 2019 [°C]	-3.27	-3.84	-1.14	2.48	-3.65	-1.61
Mean slope [°]	1.42	2.34	2.77	1.69	1.75	2.00
Infrastructure [%]	7	2	2	1	3	6
Fire scars [%]	23	3	13	11	10	0

204 Circumarctic land cover units (CALU) are available from a fusion of
 205 Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 (Bartsch et al., 2024a)). CALU is provided at 10m
 206 spatial sampling and is based on data from 2016-2024. The original version
 207 covered tundra regions only. The extended dataset (version 2, Bartsch et al.
 208 (2024b)) also includes selected areas of the tundra-forest transition zone and
 209 covers all of the selected study areas. The units represent areas of similar
 210 reflectance and have been assigned specific vegetation and soil properties
 211 (wetness, soil mineral content, shrub physiognomy etc.). The majority and
 212 diversity (number of units with at least 1% coverage) were derived based on
 213 1 km x 1 km gridding as applied for heterogeneity assessment in Bartsch
 214 et al. (2024a).

215 Mean annual ground temperature (MAGT) and active layer thickness
 216 time series are available from the ESA CCI Permafrost project (v4 West-
 217 ermann et al. (2024)). They are derived through a thermal model driven
 218 and constrained by satellite data (MODIS LST) where available. In case of
 219 MAGT, data representing a depth of 2 m have been selected for comparison
 220 to the deformation rates. The regions represent a gradient of permafrost
 221 MAGT and zones, including transition areas where mean regional MAGT is
 222 above 0°C (Table 3).

223

224 Air temperature was required for the seasonal deformation derivative
225 across the entire study regions. It was derived from ERA5 reanalysis data
226 which combines model information with observations to produce a globally
227 consistent dataset (Hersbach et al., 2023). We used air temperature at 2 m
228 above the surface in a temporal resolution of 2 hours at 0.25° spatial resolu-
229 tion as suggested in Widhalm et al. (2025).

230

231 The SACHI dataset (Sentinel-1/2 derived Arctic Coastal Human Impact,
232 Bartsch et al. (2023b)) was used to identify the fraction of infrastructure in
233 each region. For the purpose of this study, a 2 km buffer was applied around
234 all features, including roads, buildings and other human impacted areas.

235

236 **3. Methodology**

237 *3.1. Deformation retrieval*

238 The workflow included multi-looking, topographic phase removal and fil-
239 tering. Several measures were taken in order to handle errors from atmo-
240 spheric and ionospheric effects including spatial filtering and averaging over
241 several years.

242 Interferograms were processed sequentially in a daisy-chain network for
243 seasonal analyses. For Sentinel-1 multi-annual retrieval, seasonal time series
244 were linked using interferograms that connect the end of one season to the
245 end of the following year's season. In the case of PALSAR-2 all possible
246 interferogram combinations were calculated and pairs were only selected in
247 case of sufficient coherence. They were multi-looked with a factor of 5 by
248 1 pixels for Sentinel-1 and 2 by 9 pixels for PALSAR-2. The Copernicus
249 DEM with 30 m spatial resolution was used for topographic phase removal.
250 Adaptive phase filtering (Goldstein and Werner, 1998) was applied before
251 unwrapping (Costantini, 1998). Vertical deformation was derived through
252 multi-baseline InSAR (Berardino et al., 2002). In order to correct for at-
253 mospheric and ionospheric effects spatial filtering (filter radius ~ 20 km) was
254 applied to derive a layer for correction. The assumption is that the filtered
255 raster contains all distortions introduced by variations in the atmosphere and
256 ionosphere. In case of Sentinel-1, atmosphere correction based on GACOS
257 (Generic Atmospheric Correction Online Service for InSAR) data (workflow
258 details available in Widhalm et al. (2025)) was applied in selected cases in
259 order to investigate the impact of the correction technique on the results.

260 Eventually, all results were terrain-corrected and geocoded.

261

262 Seasonal deformation was derived from Sentinel-1 exploiting the compara-
263 bly high data density. Multi-year deformation was obtained from PALSAR-2
264 and from Sentinel-1 where possible.

265

266 *3.2. Sentinel-1 seasonal deformation rate, $-\alpha_{DDT}$*

267 Seasonal analyses is using acquisitions starting close to the start of thaw
268 which has been determined with ERA5 data. Depending on region and year,
269 this varied between mid May and mid June. The final date was chosen close
270 to freeze-up, usually early to mid September. Years were included into the
271 analyses when at least five valid interferograms could be obtained.

272

273 Variations in seasonal subsidence between the years are driven by air
274 temperature fluctuations (Bartsch et al., 2019). Cumulative positive degree
275 days/degree days of thaw (DDT) were therefore used instead of date or day
276 of year to analyze the time series. The use of DDT allows the comparison
277 and combination of different years (Bartsch et al., 2019). DDT was derived
278 from ERA5 data following the approach of Widhalm et al. (2025). The sea-
279 sonal deformation rate (deformation per DDT, here referred to as $-\alpha_{DDT}$)
280 was determined assuming a linear relationship between air temperature and
281 subsidence. Widhalm et al. (2025) defined α_{DDT} representing subsidence as
282 positive for the purpose of soil moisture retrieval. Here, we treat subsidence
283 as negative and thus derive $-\alpha_{DDT}$. The median from all available years
284 has been used for further analyses.

285

286 *3.3. Mosaic-ing, sub-setting and masking*

287 The focus of the analyses was on permafrost lowlands. Subsets of the
288 chosen scenes were therefore defined based on landscape features such as
289 mountain ranges and river floodplains. The latter were largely masked as
290 part of the InSAR processing (areas with loss of interferometric coherence).
291 Mountain ranges have been excluded in case of Inuvik (area west of the
292 Mackenzie River floodplain). Pixels for which the slope exceeds 5° (Coper-
293 nicus DEM) have been masked in all regions.

294

295 In case of Yamal, seasonal deformation derived from nine frames was
296 used in order to match the size of the corresponding PALSAR-2 scene. A
297 weighted mean merging scheme has been implemented for the overlap areas.
298 A weighted feathering method was applied in the overlapping areas of each
299 scene pair. In a first step the weighted mask was computed for the over-
300 lapping areas of the scenes only. The weights were calculated so that they
301 gradually decrease from the center of the overlap regions toward the edges
302 based on distance. These weights were then normalized so that their sum
303 equaled one in the overlapping areas. The final mosaic was generated by
304 multiplying images with their respective weights and summing the results.
305 The feathering method is applied to smooth the transition between overlap-
306 ping and non-overlapping areas. The values in the non-overlapping parts
307 remained unchanged.
308

309 *3.4. Aggregation and resampling*

310 Each of the selected study regions encompasses landscape variations in
311 terrain, vegetation and soil conditions. Auxiliary data of soil properties (type,
312 temperature, active layer) are, however, only available in spatially general-
313 ized form. To enable comparison at a consistent resolution, deformation
314 results were averaged over $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ areas, and all other datasets were
315 resampled to the same $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ grid. Fires scar age information has
316 been transformed into three classes: older than 1980, 1980 - 2009, younger
317 than 2009.
318

319 The considered parameters represent categorial information (soil type, in-
320 frastructure, fire age group, land cover derivatives) as well as biogeophysical
321 parameters (MAGT, ALT, NDVI) and terrain (slope).
322

323 *3.5. Parameter testing*

324 A Random Forest Regressor machine learning model was employed to an-
325 alyze the relationship between the selected raster-based features and ground
326 deformation as the target variable. The Random Forest Model was trained
327 for each feature raster, with the dataset split into 80% for training and 20%
328 for testing. Systematic hyperparameter tuning was performed according to
329 Table 4. Cross-validation was used for hyperparameter tuning to ensure a
330 robust model selection. The R^2 score was derived to evaluate the accuracy

Table 4: Parameters used for systematic hyperparameter tuning in the Random Forest model

Parameter Name	Tested Variables
n estimators	100, 200, 300
max depth	10, 20, None
min samples split	2, 5, 10
min samples leaf	1, 2, 5
max features	sqrt, log2

331 of the model’s prediction. Negative values, which indicate predictions worse
 332 than the mean model, have been set to zero. Parameter importance was
 333 tested in addition.

334 4. Results

335 4.1. Time series availability

336 Atmospheric and ionospheric errors could not be satisfactorily addressed
 337 for some years in both Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2. The differences in data
 338 availability in addition resulted in varying covered periods across the sites
 339 and sensors (Tables 1 and 2). Eventually 150 interferograms were used for
 340 long-term and 192 for seasonal deformation retrieval. Long-term time se-
 341 ries started partially in 2015 and in one case ended in 2021. All PALSAR-2
 342 records finished latest in 2019 due to a change in acquisition strategy for
 343 Arctic regions afterwards. Suitable multi-year interferograms from Sentinel-
 344 1 could be integrated until 2021. PALSAR-2 and Sentinel-1 records have
 345 been partially complementing each other as intended. Overlap was achieved
 346 only for the central North Slope and Noatak. The Inuvik time series included
 347 records from both missions but distinct years.

348
 349 Seasonal retrieval started with 2017 when data became available regularly
 350 across the Arctic land areas and ended in 2021 for Russian sites (failure of
 351 Sentinel-1 B, see Figure 1) and the last season used covered 2023 for Northern
 352 America. The length of records and gaps are otherwise determined through
 353 availability of early season (May/June) data. In single cases, atmospheric
 354 and ionospheric effects have been too strong across the season. Eventually,
 355 there has not been a single year with coverage for all six sites. The best year
 356 was 2020 with five sites covered.

357

358 *4.2. Regional differences for long-term deformation*

359 Data distributions for each region exhibited a near-Gaussian shape af-
360 ter spatial filtering (Figure 3). The spread of spatially filtered deformation
361 values differs across regions for both PALSAR-2 and Sentinel-1 (Figure 3).
362 Results for the North Slope are similar, although only a partial overlap in
363 years exists. Larger differences between the sensors were found for Noatak
364 and Inuvik. Yukon and Chersky showed a similar pattern. Both records have
365 the highest spread with long-term rates ± 2 cm/year, compared to the other
366 sites where they are well below 1cm/year. In case of Chersky, specifically
367 patches of old fire scars show positive values and river floodplain negative
368 values (Figure 4). The spread across the Yukon region is dominated by fire
369 scars of different stages (positive and negative deformation values).

370
371 For the spatially filtered PALSAR-2 data, the standard deviation across
372 the regions is in the order of 0.5 to 1 cm/year (Table 5) for the full records.
373 This pattern is similar for GACOS corrected results. The mean, however,
374 deviates as GACOS processing does not centre the data around zero. Conse-
375 quently, the GACOS-corrected results exhibit a tendency toward either subsi-
376 dence or heave, with scene averages differing from zero. The North Slope and
377 Noatak sites showed average subsidence rates of 0.3 and 0.9 cm/year respec-
378 tively. Inuvik and Chersky showed on average heave (more than 1cm/year).

379
380 The standard deviation of the regional deformation rates does not only
381 differ between regions but can also differ when altering the time period. For
382 example, it can be > 2 cm as in case of Noatak when considering only the
383 overlap period of Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2 (shorter time period, two instead
384 of three years) (Table 5). PALSAR-2 spatially filtered results showed, how-
385 ever, a standard deviation in a similar order as Sentinel-1.

386
387 Positive values were observed for specific land cover types in the Noatak
388 and Chersky regions after spatial filtering (Figure 5). This occurs for Sentinel-
389 1 as well as PALSAR-2 in case of Noatak. Dry tundra and barren areas had
390 positive values in both regions. In case of Noatak, this also applied to moist
391 to wet tundra.

392

Table 5: Long-term deformation statistics (mean and standard deviation, in m/year): comparison between spatial filtering (SF) and GACOS correction. Noatak 1: 2019-2021, Noatak 2: 2019-2020.

Type	Method	North Slope	Inuvik	Noatak 1	Noatak 2	Chersky
Mean	S1 GACOS	-0.0031	0.0127	-0.0086	-	0.0139
Mean	S1 SF	0.0004	0.0001	0.0006	0.0014	-0.0004
Mean	PALSAR-2 SF	-	-	-	-0.0005	-
STD	S1 GACOS	0.0069	0.0131	0.0101	-	0.0189
STD	S1 SF	0.0054	0.0118	0.0092	0.0230	0.0143
STD	PALSAR-2 SF	-	-	-	0.0170	-

393 4.3. Regional differences for seasonal deformation

394 Seasonal deformation rates, expressed as $-\alpha DDT$ based on Sentinel-1,
 395 vary according to land cover (Figure 6). Wetlands and disturbed (largely
 396 representing fire scars) areas show on average negative values across most
 397 regions. Distinct positive values are obtained for barren areas. Depending
 398 on region, this also applies to partially barren, dry tundra. This pattern is
 399 pronounced for Noatak, Chersky and Yamal. A further common pattern for
 400 these three regions is a tendency for negative values for moist tundra types
 401 which are predominating (see also Figure 2). Positive values were determined
 402 for forest in most cases.

404 4.4. Long-term versus seasonal deformation

405 Fire affected areas show comparably high seasonal subsidence (negative
 406 $-\alpha DDT$) in regions where they occur frequently (e.g. Chersky and Noatak,
 407 Figure 9). The long-term tendency varies, positive as well as negative values
 408 were observed. The surroundings of infrastructure on the North Slope and
 409 Noatak subsides seasonally more than on average within the scenes. Drained
 410 lake basins in the North Slope area also show seasonal subsidence but less
 411 pronounced as for areas with infrastructure. No distinct long-term signal
 412 can be observed in these cases. This differs for Noatak where infrastructure
 413 subsides according to both, Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2 time series. An ex-
 414 treme case of long-term subsidence (on average -1.4 cm) is apparent when
 415 separating the area of the Bovanenkovo gas field on Yamal (Figure 9).

417 4.5. Factor analyses

418 The R^2 score has been comparably small in all long-term cases (< 0.3 ,
419 indicating a weak model fit. But differences can be observed across the
420 deformation derivatives and regions (Figure 10). Land cover majority and
421 disturbances (fires), separate and in combination, have the highest scores.
422 Specifically fires could be confirmed relevant for seasonal as well as long-
423 term deformation. Land cover, and to a lesser degree, NDVI are linked to
424 seasonal deformation. Slope can regionally play a role for seasonal deforma-
425 tion. This is for example the case for Noatak (NRB). A moderate model fit
426 (values > 0.3) could be obtained for seasonal deformation when combining
427 land cover and fire. The joint consideration of all parameters resulted in an
428 R^2 score around 0.5 for seasonal deformation.

429
430 NDVI and slope could be identified as parameters of comparably high
431 importance in most cases (Figure 10). Land cover majority, wetland fraction
432 and MAGT are of lower importance, but higher than for active layer thick-
433 ness, land cover diversity, infrastructure and soil texture.

435 5. Discussion

436 5.1. InSAR processing

437 Several factors were substantially limiting the InSAR retrieval. Main
438 issues included:

- 439 • limited data availability through mission acquisition strategies
- 440 • mismatch in acquisition versus early season timing of start of thaw and
441 late season end of thaw
- 442 • limited suitability of available tools for correction of atmospheric and
443 ionospheric effects

444 Although that Sentinel-1 has been launched in 2014, only seven years
445 could be used for deformation analyses across the Arctic. The first relevant
446 unfrozen season overlapped with the commissioning phase of Sentinel-1 A
447 as well as -1 B and acquisition strategies in the early years did not favor Ar-
448 ctic land areas. The loss of Sentinel-1 B again constrained data availability.
449 This might have been also one of the reasons that Sentinel-1 has rarely been

450 used for long-term deformation retrieval in high latitude permafrost regions
451 although its applicability has been demonstrated by Strozzi et al. (2018),
452 despite the comparably short wavelength.

453

454 A mismatch of acquisition availability and start of thaw can be addressed
455 through the use of DDT and the assumption of a linear relationship between
456 deformation and DDT (Bartsch et al., 2019). This is applicable for seasonal
457 analyses. Long-term retrievals should ideally be based on a start and end
458 with similar DDT to ensure that no seasonal signal is impacting the results.
459 Liu et al. (2010) applied a model which considered secular and seasonal sub-
460 sidence to match and interpret sporadic acquisitions from ERS within the
461 seasonal cycle. The pattern is, however, not always uniform, as for example
462 in unusually warm years (Bartsch et al., 2019; Zwieback and Meyer, 2021).
463 The scarce sampling has been specifically a limiting factor for PALSAR-2 use
464 in our study. A Sentinel-1 versus PALSAR-2 comparison could be therefore
465 only made for a single year and region (see Table 5).

466

467 Spatial filtering of InSAR deformation time series dampens the defor-
468 mation magnitude as exemplified for permafrost environments in Widhalm
469 et al. (2025). The regional average is shifted close to zero, independent from
470 the original tendency for either subsidence or heave (Figure 12). The near-
471 Gaussian shape after spatial filtering (Figure 3) can be partly explained by
472 the Central Limit Theorem, which states that the aggregation of multiple
473 independent sources of variability tends to produce a normal distribution. In
474 this case, the distribution of each region constitutes of spatial and temporal
475 variability at local and regional scales.

476

477 The data distribution pattern of spatially filtered data are similar to
478 GACOS filtered (Table 5) and thus potentially allow within scene relative
479 change investigations. But total deformation is reduced. Land cover com-
480 parisons demonstrate that the barren class tends to have higher positive
481 values than others. This land cover class often represents bedrock and can
482 be therefore expected as stable. It could thus be potentially considered for
483 bias correction.

484

485 The use of approaches such as GACOS can provide an alternative to spa-
486 tial filtering, but there are issues related to the general quality of the modeled
487 atmosphere data across the Arctic and the limitation of data to certain day

488 times which can differ from the acquisition timing by several hours (Widhalm
489 et al., 2025). In addition, ionospheric impacts remain to be addressed.

490

491 As noted in Fan et al. (2025), seasonal deformation can reach levels
492 that cause unwrapping errors in long-span interferometric pairs in C-band
493 Sentinel-1 data. They recommended using 12-day interferograms as reliable
494 references for correction. In our study, we also implemented this approach by
495 employing a daisy-chain network using the shortest temporal baseline inter-
496 ferograms, provided their quality allowed for such usage in seasonal Sentinel-1
497 analysis. This method was also previously suggested by Strozzi et al. (2018).
498 Like in Strozzi et al. (2018), for the year to year connection of Sentinel-1
499 data we opted for the usage of interferograms from end of the summer rather
500 than winter as was suggested by Fan et al. (2025), as a connection to winter
501 seasons was oftentimes omitted by snow melt or snow fall leading to decor-
502 relation.

503

504 Eventually, a comparison across the selected sites for a same year with
505 the same sensor could not be achieved in our study. Spatially and temporally
506 consistent coverage is expected to become available from new missions such
507 as NISAR (Rosen and Kumar, 2021) and through the extension of Sentinel-1
508 with C and D and ALOS-2 with ALOS-4. Considering the commissioning
509 phase and time constraint to the northern hemisphere unfrozen season, suit-
510 able acquisitions can potentially be expected only for 2026 onward.

511

512 *5.2. Deformation patterns*

513 Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2 long-term deformation distribution patterns
514 matched for the central North Slope and differed in case of Inuvik and
515 Noatak (Figure 7). Spatial patterns showed nevertheless similarities for In-
516 uvik (Figure 4). This might be related to remaining issues of atmosphere
517 and ionosphere effects, but could be also linked to the wavelength difference
518 or mismatch of temporal overlap. Inuvik includes substantial forest areas.
519 More signal interaction is expected with the shorter wavelength C-band than
520 for longer wavelength L-band. Slope processes might play a role as well. Ar-
521 eas with $> 5^\circ$ were masked, but the terrain model (Copernicus DEM) might
522 not fully reflect actual slope patterns. Sentinel-1 images were acquired in
523 descending and PALSAR-2 in ascending orbit in this region (Table 1). This
524 leads to different viewing angles. Slope movements towards or away from

525 the sensor can appear as heave or subsidence patterns. Depending on terrain
526 variations, the cumulative effects may differ between ascending and descend-
527 ing orbits. Opposing patterns between Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2 can for
528 example be observed for the northern and northeastern part of the analyzed
529 area for Inuvik (Figure 4). This region is known for slope movements, specif-
530 ically thaw slumping has been reported (Kokelj et al., 2023).

531
532 Positive $-\alpha DDT$ values were observed for forested areas with C-band
533 (Figure 6). In case of Inuvik, mean $-\alpha DDT$ for Sentinel-1 are, however,
534 shifted towards subsidence compared to PALSAR-2 results (Figure 3). The
535 higher spread and lower peak value in the Sentinel-1 Inuvik as well as Noatak
536 results might point to higher noise and thus probably atmosphere and iono-
537 sphere effects. The larger spread in Sentinel-1 can be also observed across
538 all land cover types for Inuvik (Figure 5).

539
540 A larger spread of the density distribution also occurred for the Yukon-
541 Kuskokwim Delta long-term results. In case of Chersky, different landscape
542 types are covered (Widhalm et al., 2025). Not only forest areas are included,
543 also river floodplains, extensive fire scars and the eastern part of the Kolyma
544 lowlands (alluvial marine deposits, Shmelev et al. (2017)) which show distinct
545 seasonal (Widhalm et al., 2025) and long-term deformation patterns (Figure
546 4). The phenomena might also contribute to the larger spread of deformation
547 rates as was also suggested by Guan et al. (2024) in case of high landscape
548 and thus deformation diversity. The range of deformation values might also
549 be influenced by seasonal variations (e.g. increase in wet dry gradients).

550
551 Positive values for long-term retrievals and the seasonal $-\alpha DDT$ were
552 observed for distinct land cover types after the spatial filtering. In addition
553 to barren areas, positive $-\alpha DDT$ can be also observed for specifically dryer
554 areas which are covered by lichen and only prostrate shrubs (Figure 6). In
555 case of Noatak and Chersky this patterns coincides with long-term heave
556 contrary to Yamal (Figure 5). This suggests that this seasonal phenomenon
557 might not be directly linked to ground ice, a process in general associated
558 with long-term deformation (Streletskiy et al., 2025). The slope α was ob-
559 tained from subsequent InSAR pairs over a specific unfrozen season. This
560 means in case of positive $-\alpha DDT$, continuously increasing positive defor-
561 mation values occurred after filtering. Assuming that soils are more wet
562 after snow melt and landscapes, especially uplands, show a drying pattern

563 on the surface afterwards, a higher diversity and thus spread of values can
564 be expected. The larger time steps may also result in higher noise increasing
565 the spread of the density distribution. Figure 11 exemplifies such a case for
566 Chersky and central Yamal. This might result eventually in a positive slope
567 α . Drying is also expected to rather lead to false detection of subsidence
568 due to the larger signal penetration depth than heave (e.g. Zwieback et al.
569 (2016)).

570

571 Actual heave may be caused by ground ice aggradation. However, heave
572 has so far only been unambiguously attributed in cases such as pingo growth
573 (Samsonov et al., 2016) and fire recovery (Michaelides et al., 2019). Other
574 proposed mechanisms include moss build-up (Zwieback et al., 2024b), colder
575 post-flooding temperatures (Zwieback et al., 2023), and pronounced frost
576 heave in autumn which exceeds the preceding subsidence (Guan et al., 2024).
577 However, spatial filtering centers the mean deformation within a scene to ap-
578 proximately zero (Figure 12). Areas of heave might thus represent stable
579 areas or even subsidence. Five of the in situ subsidence measurement sites of
580 O'Neill et al. (2023) are located within the area processed for Inuvik. Their
581 average deformation rate for 1992 to 2018 was -0.8 cm/year, with a range
582 of -0.35 cm/year to -1.9 cm/year. The average long-term rate from spa-
583 tially filtered PALSAR-2 (2016-2018) was -0.16 cm/year and from Sentinel-1
584 (2019-2020) it was -0.25 cm/year for these locations. These rates might be
585 in the order of -0.4 to -0.6 cm/year respectively (Figure 5) when considering
586 a potential bias introduced through the spatial filtering.

587

588 Unfiltered or GACOS filtered results point even towards more heave in-
589 stead of subsidence (Figure 12) with on average 1.3 cm/year (Table 5).
590 Zwieback et al. (2023) argued that InSAR observed heave patterns of less
591 than 2 cm were within the standard error. Only extreme settings such as
592 burned area can thus reliably be studied.

593

594 A density distribution centered around zero was also found by Guan et al.
595 (2024), who suggested that all areas with less than zero can be considered as
596 permafrost degradation sites. In general this applied to less than half of the
597 regions. More extensive independent validation is needed to evaluate such
598 concepts considering the spatial filtering impact on the density distribution.

599

600 Differences in direction of deformation as can be observed for fire scars

601 (Figure 9) reflect the fire timing. Younger scars exhibit subsidence (e.g. for
602 Sentinel-1 Yanagiya and Furuya (2020)) and older fire scars are known to
603 show heave after several decades (Michaelides et al., 2019). The surround-
604 ing of infrastructure was found to be partially characterized by pronounced
605 seasonal subsidence. Long-term subsidence could be identified for the Bova-
606 nenkovo gas field what agrees with Teshebaeva et al. (2021), but the mag-
607 nitude differed. The average rate found for 2017-2029 was approximately
608 1.5 cm per year, what is much lower than the 12 cm subsidence identified
609 with the persistent scatterer technique for a 16 month period (2017 to 2018)
610 by Teshebaeva et al. (2021). Potentially, the spatial filtering might dampen
611 the values in this case. Liu et al. (2010) determined pronounced subsidence
612 in the proximity of the Prudoe Bay Oil field, but also with lower rates, in
613 the order of 4-7 cm per decade. Two further hotspots of subsidence were
614 found in tundra areas of central Yamal by Teshebaeva et al. (2021) which
615 could not be identified in our results. This might relate to the difference in
616 processing techniques and/or spatial filtering. Teshebaeva et al. (2021) also
617 tested different DEMs, but limited to the areas of the deformation hotspots.
618 The SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) DEM (2000) was compared
619 to the TandemX-DEM (2014). The average difference was approximately
620 2 m (corresponding to > 10 cm per year) what could also originate from
621 a general bias between the DEM products. In situ rates of more than 10
622 cm per year have been so far only reported from infrastructure related dis-
623 turbance (Streletskiy et al., 2025). Similar alternatives to InSAR analyses
624 (DEM differencing) have been tested for specifically fire scars and polygo-
625 nal degradation features. Airborne laser scanning can provide very detailed
626 information (e.g. Jones et al. (2024); Douglas et al. (2021)) but is rarely
627 available. Satellite laser altimetry can be used to identify the presence of a
628 seasonal signal, but precise deformation quantification in permafrost areas
629 remains challenging Michaelides et al. (2021).

630

631 5.3. Factor analyses

632 Disturbance patterns clearly play a role specifically in regions with more
633 fires. Land cover has, however, the highest R^2 score across all tested param-
634 eters, sites, sensors and deformation types (seasonal versus long-term; Figure
635 10). The central North Slope had the lowest model fitting score. This region
636 is more homogeneous than the others (Figure 2) and also does not show a
637 large variation in long-term deformation (Figure 4). Vegetation patterns,

638 partially reflected also in land cover, are of importance for seasonal defor-
639 mation over Yamal. This applies to specifically dry lichen dominated tundra
640 (Figure 8), which is more common in this region than in the others (Figure
641 2). Wetness is known to drive vegetation patterns in this region. For example
642 the comparably large willow shrubs (*Salix*) occur predominately in riverine
643 and lacustrine wetlands (Dvornikov et al., 2016). Slope could be identified
644 as partially important although only lowlands ($< 5^\circ$) were considered. This
645 reflects redistribution of water and might also point to slope movements, as
646 indicated through the comparison between long-term results from ascending
647 and descending orbit (Figure 4). The change of data distribution through
648 the spatial filtering might also have an impact on the scores of the model
649 fitting. Overall, the model fitting using the selected parameters was more
650 successful for seasonal than for long-term deformation.

651

652 Previously, soil type and active active layer thickness were identified as
653 linked what could not be confirmed with our results. This might to a large
654 extent result from the lack of information at the required scale and accuracy.
655 Active layer thickness was obtained from modelling results which also de-
656 pend on external information on soils (Westermann et al., 2015) what leads
657 to high uncertainties in the retrieval. The comparably high importance of
658 NDVI for seasonal deformation partially agrees with findings of Wig et al.
659 (2025), who considered NDVI trends.

660

661 **6. Conclusions**

662 The availability of Sentinel-1 time series allowed specifically the analyses
663 of seasonal thaw progression itself and comparison to long-term deformation
664 in permafrost landscapes. Building consistent records posed a major chal-
665 lenge. A more consistent coverage by future missions is expected to yield
666 a major step forward for characterization of lowland permafrost landscapes
667 and areas of degradation across the Arctic with SAR interferometry. Dense
668 observation intervals in May, June and September support adaption to year
669 to year changes with respect to the beginning and end of the thaw period.
670 PALSAR-2 data could be shown to complement the Sentinel-1 timeseries for
671 long-term analyses.

672

673 Vegetation patterns in tundra regions are partially linked to seasonal
674 deformation. Disturbance patterns, specifically fires are most relevant for
675 long-term deformation. The analyses of positive deformation patterns needs
676 more attention. Specifically, the choice of methods for treatment of atmo-
677 spheric effects is important and needs to be considered when absolute values
678 are interpreted.

679

680 The Random Forest regression results indicate the potential utility of
681 land cover and vegetation information for the prediction of deformation pat-
682 terns, but model fitting scores are only weak to moderate. The selected
683 parameters were more applicable for seasonal than for long-term deforma-
684 tion. Nevertheless, as in situ observations are very scarce, the provision of
685 reliable deformation rates from remote sensing remains crucial for monitor-
686 ing and understanding permafrost degradation across Arctic lowlands.

687

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Figure 1: Location of used frames (Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2), including examples of Sentinel-1 availability during the unfrozen period, number of years for which at least six acquisitions were available and permafrost presence 2020 in % (1 km grid; source: Westermann et al. (2024)). 2021 represents Sentinel-1 A and B, 2022 A only. Tundra/CAVM boundary source: Walker et al. (2002).

Figure 2: Land cover majority and land cover diversity across the study regions within 1 km x 1 km areas (source: CALU - Circumarctic Landcover Units Bartsch et al. (2024b)). Regions: IN - Inuvik, NS - central North Slope, NRB - Noatak River Basin, YKD - Yukon-Kuskokwim Delta, CH - Chersky, YAM - Yamal. CALU classes: W - wetland, WAT - wet to aquatic tundra, MWT - moist to wet tundra, DMT - dry to moist tundra, DT - dry tundra, DAT - dry to aquatic tundra, MT - moist tundra, F - forest.

Figure 3: Density distribution of spatially filtered annual deformation rates (spatially filtered) from Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2.

Figure 4: Long-term deformation maps (spatially filtered) obtained from Sentinel-1 (left) and PALSAR-2 (right). Burned area extent sources: Alaska Large Fire Database (Kasischke et al., 2002) starting 1940, Fire History by NWT Centre for Geomatics starting 1950 and MODIS (Lizundia-Loiola et al., 2020)/Landsat for Chersky starting 1993.

Figure 5: Sentinel-1 and PALSAR-2 long-term deformation (spatially filtered) by land cover (source: Bartsch et al. (2024a)), left Sentinel-1, right PALSAR-2. For land cover legend see caption of Figure 2.

Figure 6: Sentinel-1 seasonal deformation (spatially filtered) by land cover (source: Bartsch et al. (2024a)). For land cover legend see caption of Figure 2.

Figure 7: Correlation between long-term and seasonal deformation.

Figure 8: Results based on spatial filtering for the Yamal region (1 km x 1 km mean): Spatially filtered PALSAR-2 deformation rate, Sentinel-1 seasonal deformation, correlation long-term versus seasonal, and land cover majority (source Bartsch et al. (2024a); for abbreviations see Figure 2).

Figure 9: Long-term versus seasonal deformation (spatially filtered) including examples for subsets of fire disturbance (sources: Kasischke et al. (2002), Lizundia-Loiola et al. (2020), Landsat), drained lake basins (North Slope, source: Bergstedt et al. (2021)) and infrastructure (source: Bartsch et al. (2020b)) for Sentinel-1 versus Sentinel-1 (top row) and PALSAR-2 versus Sentinel-1 (bottom row) for selected regions.

Figure 10: Random Forest factor analyses results. Left: R^2 score (negative values have been set to 0.0 as indicator for imperfect prediction); right: parameter importance.

Figure 11: Density distribution for Sentinel-1 derived seasonal deformation rates for Chersky and central Yamal before (top) and after (bottom) spatial filtering.

Figure 12: Density distribution for Sentinel-1 derived long-term deformation rates for selected sites. a) original, b) GACOS corrected, c) spatially filtered.